

Designing data-driven learning and development strategies: Evidence from the banking industry

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Introduction

The Learning and Development (L&D) strategies play a pivotal role in nurturing the workforce to adapt to the rapidly evolving technological and analytical landscape. (Porath 2023, Boot et al 2008).

The L&D approach under consideration is a collaborative effort between the bank's internal L&D team, spearheaded by a Middle Manager, and an outsourced L&D team consisting of four dedicated resources. This partnership aims to address the unique challenges and opportunities within the BAO, which comprises distinct verticals, namely Business Analysts, Data Engineering, Data Science, and Reporting Analysts.

Within each vertical, there are distinct cohorts comprising Trainees, Middle Managers, Senior Managers, and Top Leaders. The current learning metrics are primarily based on learning hours, with each cohort eligible for Silver, Gold, and Platinum Certificates based on their annual completion of learning hours. The certificate criteria vary for each cohort, presumably keeping diverse learning needs and expectations at different organizational levels into consideration.

Business Analyst (BA)	332
Data Engineer (DE)	179
Data Scientist (DS)	67
Reporting Analyst (RA)	191
Total	769

Fig-1: Bank Analytics Organization (BAO) Verticals

Trainee	145
Middle Manager	505
Senior Manager	119
Total	769

Fig-2: Bank Analytics Organization (BAO) Cohorts

	Silver	Gold	Platinum	Target / M
Trainee	70	90	110	15
Middle Manager	40	60	80	6
Senior Manager	30	50	60	5

Fig-3: Present System of Cohort Wise Learning Hours Targets and Reward Criteria

Individual Learning Journeys have been meticulously designed by the outsourced L&D team, offering a tailored approach for Trainees, Middle Managers, and Senior Managers, with further specialization within each vertical. These learning journeys encompass Technical, Tools, Process, Functional, and Professional domains, providing a comprehensive framework for skill development. There are 13 learning journeys in total (12 for the Trainee, Middle Managers, Senior Managers and 1 for the Senior Leadership cohort). The learning journey for senior leadership has 3 components:

- Self-paced learning
- Book Reading: Book review interventions are conducted wherein a particular book is chosen and leaders share insights on that.
- Senior Leadership Talks (Leaders learn by teaching)

Interestingly, the Senior Leadership cohort hasn't got the learning hours target.

The training modes incorporated in the L&D strategy include Self-paced learning through platforms like Coursera, Virtual Instructor-Led Live Training (VILT), In-Person Instructor-Led Training (ILT), and other accessible formats such as PDFs and YouTube tutorials. Each cohort is assigned specific monthly learning targets, acknowledging the diverse needs and responsibilities at different organizational levels.

Although the learning goals kept for Trainees, Middle Managers and Senior Managers appear liberal (less than 2 hours per week), yet they are struggling to achieve them.

Despite the well-structured L&D framework, BAO faces several challenges. Workload and time constraints emerge as primary obstacles for employees to achieve their learning targets. Additionally, some employees find the relevance and application of the learning journeys to their roles unclear, contributing to a gap in engagement. Accessibility issues, lack of clarity on learning journeys, and a predominantly push-based learning culture further compound the challenges faced by the L&D team.

This research endeavours to critically examine the existing L&D strategies, assess the challenges faced, and propose innovative solutions to enhance the effectiveness of the learning culture within the BAO. By addressing these challenges, the research aims to contribute valuable insights to the broader discourse on designing L&D strategies in analytics-driven sectors within the banking industry.

Literature Review

In one study wide range of theoretical, historical and empirical literature on banking models and detailed case analyses of failing and non-failing banks is examined. The study finds that a lack of basic knowledge of banking risks and value drivers by the boards and senior managers of the failing banks was implicated in the banking crisis. These knowledge problems concerned banks' understanding of their organisation, intermediation and risk management in an active market setting characterised by rapid economic and organisational change. Thus, the failing banks ignored or were unaware of this knowledge and hence experienced acute difficulties with learning the new knowledge needed to address the new problems thrown up by the financial crisis. (Holland, J. 2010).

Another research paper demonstrates how a banking institution in Turkey is managing the inclusion of e-learning in its learning strategy. The case study demonstrates that the adoption of e-learning is influencing bank's learning strategy and that the simple delivery through technology cannot be sustained as a separate form of training, an appendix to traditional instructor-led activities. To be successful, it must be seen as a part of a complete learning architecture that includes a variety of tools, approaches, and a coherent learning culture. The analysis shows two emerging phenomena: • A different degree of success of the e-learning initiative depending upon its coherence with the organizational culture, and the bank's strategy • A changing balance of classroom training and e-learning in relationship to the adoption of the LMS adoption in each department. (Kok, A 2013)

A research paper in a study done in Switzerland follows the research question “how can the learning function foster the enhancement of the banking organisation’s learning and innovation ability in times of digital transformation?” This is closely linked to the kind of services a learning function needs to enhance or integrate for supporting and designing a learning organization. (Schuchmann, D et al, 2015)

Findings from a study done in Jordan banking sector indicate that training and development is not driven by human resource strategy and that it is reactive rather than proactive. Training and development do improve skills, knowledge, attitudes and behaviours but there is little evidence that it increases commitment and satisfaction nor that it contributes to strategic aims in any significant way. The linkages between strategy and training and development are not explicit and strategies are not interpreted through performance management systems. (Rowland CA et al, 2017)

A study investigated the impact that educational technology has on training and development downtime, accessibility with regard to different learning platforms, return on investment (ROI), organisational culture and learning within the banking environment in a leading bank in South Africa. The study revealed that the bank has a strong organisational culture; and educational technology at the bank showed positive results with regard to decreasing downtime and seeing increased ROI. (Razia Khan et al, 2017)

Results from a study done in Karachi, Pakistan showed a positive impact of training and development and internal communication on engagement. Findings of the study have the potential of practical implication for managers and employees alike where they can increase engagement level in banking sector through strategic and tactical communication process and fulfilling the training needs of employees to meet the requirement of current job settings. (Siddiqui, D. A. et al, 2019)

Results from another study done in Pakistan showed that in private banks, professionalism and empowerment significantly get improved under modern methods in contrast with traditional methods at public banks. Moreover, findings also revealed that professionalism and empowerment are positively affected by the modern methods of training whereas there is non-significant impact of traditional training on empowerment and professionalism. Permanent employees showed greater professionalism and empowerment as compared to contractual employees. (Faridi, A, 2019)

In research done in Ireland it was found that Learning and Development positively impacts Employee Engagement, however Learning and Development is not the most important engagement factor for employees, although it contributes significantly to engagement of employees. Instead, employees are more motivated by some other factors such as management, remuneration, interaction with colleagues, to mention but a few. (Ozoemenam, U. C. 2020)

Another paper seeks to propose a conceptual framework for defining the relationship between training and development and retaining employees through job satisfaction as the intermediary variable in Yemen's banking sector. The results of this paper are likely to emphasize the importance of training and development as a critical factor affecting job satisfaction, which in turn affects employee retention in the banking sector in Yemen. (Alrazehi, H, 2020)

A survey was conducted among 7673 employees of one of the major retail banks in South Africa, to determine the effectiveness of micro-learning and establish whether micro-learning is effective, as well as identify gaps and recommend strategies to close them. Through inferential statistical analysis of the data, it was concluded that learners reacted positively to micro-learning, the acquired relevant knowledge using micro-learning which improved work performance and business metrics. Although the micro-learning programme was deemed effective for the vast majority (80%) of the participants, two gaps were identified, namely, micro-learning did not fully embrace the social tenet of learning, and it is also not exempt from the distractions that learners experience. It is recommended that any organisation pursuing a micro-learning programme should incorporate a social knowledge-sharing element into the programme and provide users with tools to develop self-control and self-regulation habits needed to conquer constant distractions. (Govender, K. K et al, 2020)

(Solares, A et al, 2019) focus on how blended learning can foster 21st-century skills relevant to analytic and technical fields in Turkey.

(Mohd Nadzri et al, 2020) investigate the students' perceptions of blended learning specifically in a technical education setting and the challenges faced.

(Bülbül, T et al, 2021) examine the impact of blended learning on students' achievement in mathematics and computer programming within the context of software engineering education.

In a study done in Finland, it was found that Learning and Development programs have become a strategic branding tool, pushing companies to develop more facilitative and participative management styles. The trend, as stated by some respondents, is nothing new but it has gathered more momentum in the last two years. In essence, companies are now directing more of their resources on digital technologies in order to keep up with new hybrid and remote work models. (Mukulikilwa, E. 2022)

A study was done on experience of 11 of the largest IT Service Providers in India and based on in-depth interviews. The findings suggest that while traditional human resource practices are important, senior executives should take a strategic approach in developing human resource practices with knowledge and learning capabilities as central piece for organizational innovation. (Kong E et al, 2011)

Another paper reported the preliminary findings of the difference in learning organization (LO) practices across industries. It also reported the impact of knowledge management (KM) dimensions on LO and whether this impact is different across manufacturing, IT and IT-enabled services (ITES) and power generation and distribution in India. (Deepak Chawla et al, 2011)

This research proposes that national cultural dimensions of power distance, uncertainty avoidance, in-group collectivism, and future-orientation influence e-learning practices. This study distinguishes between synchronous and asynchronous methods of e-learning and the role of culture on the same.

Results from a study done in India revealed that the correlation between knowledge management and learning environment is the highest implying that knowledge and learning go hand in hand. It was also identified that the dimension learning environment bears strong association with most of the other dimensions of learning organization. Through One way ANOVA it was found that there exists a relationship between the organizational tenure of employees and dimension of learning organization. (Thakur, N et al, 2015)

A study done in India found a high level of mediating effect of learning on performance. The relationship between learning and performance was found to be 61.7 percent which implied that performance resulted from learnings and more training bring about enhanced learning which shall translate into better performance. Another significant finding was that employees who were not promoted or working in the same position for a long time did not show a

performance improvement even with training. Therefore, periodic changes in designation (promotions) would make training more effective. (Mahmood, A et al, 2020)

The current study attempts to understand the perceptions of bank employees with respect to trainings. For this purpose, a scale has been developed and consists of five dimensions: critical appreciation, soft issues, key outcomes, necessary suggestions and timing aspect. Regression analysis depicts key outcomes being the most significant factor while shorter duration of trainings are also important. Other key findings include expectations of trainees to be made partners in the learning process. (Mahmood, A et al, 2020)

In another study authors compared the learning organisation practices of Indian Businesses across sectors. It was found that profiles of Indian businesses are perceived to have low to medium level performance in dimensions of learning organisation (LO) practices across sectors. They are found to be low in internality or emotional maturity but high in strategic thrust. Among the business sectors, hotel & hospitality services & manufacturing industries have significantly higher LO scores. (Bhattacharya, S., 2017)

Theoretical Background

In this paper we are exploring following in the context of a Banking Analytics Organization:

- How does one build a learning organization?
- What are e Learning options that would engage learners better? What would be an appropriate learning mix?
- What motivates adult learners?

Learning Organization

This research is building on the fact that we live in a Volatile, Complex, Uncertain and Ambiguous world (VUCA) which demands continuous learning and development to foster adaptability. Peter Senge and a team of researchers from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) focused on building organizations with employees who can learn and share knowledge. (Fillio et al 2015) Senge classified 5 disciplines for learning.

Fig 4 – Senge's model of learning

System thinking: A conceptual cornerstone which helps bind all the other four learning discipline forces together. Senge appreciates the power of feedback generation on gap analysis and highlights the importance of balancing or stabilizing feedback. Through the systems map diagram he highlights the long-term view to be maintained in organizations. (Senge 1990:231)

Personal mastery: Organizations learn if personal learning journeys are fulfilled and its more related to the spiritual calling of individuals when it comes to performance and mastering learning. Senge highlights that it's important to realize and mindfully understand personal structural tensions, constraints, and own power during the learning journey. (Senge 1990: 139)

Mental models: The mental assumptions, pictures or images which influence our perception of the world and how we make decisions create mental models. This starts with turning the mirror inwards and understanding the capabilities or drawbacks in the learning space. In organizations, it's important to learn new capabilities and orientations for the growth of the firm and personal learnings. (Senge 1990:8)

Building a shared vision: It is important as per Senge to induce a shared vision which compels people to move towards a common goal and inspires them rather than a common vision statement with no purpose. It must be futuristic, and a disciplined approach can help galvanize both personal growth and organization vision. With the help of mental models, one can remove bottlenecks in performance to significantly improve matters. (Senge 1990:270-283)

Team learning: Personal mastery and shared vision are not enough for organisation learning and functioning. People need to be able to act together and function as a unit. Managers are responsible for building organizations where people continually expand their capabilities to understand complexity, clarify vision, and improve shared mental models. (Senge 1990)

E-Learning Styles

For determining effective e-learning styles that will be worth taking into consideration in online environments, researchers asked four open-ended questions to distance learners. Voluntarily, 161 learners answered the open-ended questions.

The questions were:

- How do you think that you learn best?
- What are you doing for remediation?
- In what way do you prefer to study?
- What precautions do you take to be more successful while studying?

The researchers analysed the qualitative data and found several emerging themes. These themes were used to reveal and clarify the properties of e-learners. Hence, after reading through the considerable literature and filter what is relevant to an online perspective, and based on the qualitative analysis of open-ended questions, and analysing learning styles proposed by Memletics Learning Style Inventory (2004), Kolb (1976), Felder and Soloman (1991), Felder Silverman Learning Model (1988), and Grasha-Reichmann Learning Style Scales (1996) in depth, researchers ended up with eight dimensions of learning styles that should be considered in online environments. These eight e-learning styles are classified as shown below. In fact, there are numerous characteristics of individuals, but for this study the main goal was to detect the most general and common aspects that can be aligned with possible instructional methods, media and materials for e-learning. (Alper, Y. G. A. 2004)

<p>Individual/Solitary Learning</p> <p>An individual learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prefers to study on their own, • reserves a long time to think about the topics related to her/his on life, • prefers to study independently with facilitation, • takes her/his own responsibility for learning, • trusts herself/himself for her/his ability to learn, • prefers to engage in asynchronous learning activities (forum, blog, wiki etc.), and • engages in group activities after self-preparation first. 	<p>Social/Collaborative Learning</p> <p>A social learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • likes to engage in interactive group activities, • places importance on communication with instructors and other learners, • prefers activities and projects that require group work, • thinks that learning is the common responsibility of the instructor and learner, • likes to facilitate and help other learners, • enjoys to engage in synchronous learning activities (chat, virtual classroom, whiteboard application etc.), and • likes to contribute and manage group work.
<p>Auditory Learning</p> <p>An auditory learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thinks that she/he learns best by “hearing”, • likes listening to music while travelling, working and studying, • loves to hear about the experiences of various people, • distinguishes between different sounds and recognizes sound, • plays an instrument or sings songs, • dislikes silent places, and • prefers instructors who explain the topic in detail. 	<p>Visual Learning</p> <p>A visual learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thinks that she/he learns best by “seeing”, • likes mostly mathematics, science and technology, • easily finds her/his way by using maps, • prefers books that contain pictures, tables and comics, • easily remembers visual objects, plans and situations, • likes art, drawing and geometry, and • enjoys taking pictures and videos of the environment.
<p>Concrete Learning</p> <p>A concrete learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thinks that she/he learns best by “doing”, • likes activities like sport and dance, • enjoys working with handcrafts like ceramics and sculpture, • likes touching objects, clothes and furniture, • enjoys learning through simulations and playing games, • likes dealing with problems needs creativity, and • enjoys exploring and researching. 	<p>Abstract Learning</p> <p>An abstract learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thinks that she/he learns best by “reading”, • links between what she/he heard and saw previously in daily conversations, • enjoys telling stories and jokes, • prefers subjects like literature, history and foreign languages, • prefers discussing problems and thoughts rather than working on them, • has a wide range of vocabulary and likes to use the right word in the right situation, and • expresses herself/himself orally or in writing very well
<p>Logical Learning</p> <p>A logical learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thinks that she/he learns best by “thinking in detail”, • likes activities requiring calculation, • likes playing logical games and solving puzzles, • prefers studying step by step with the guidance of a plan, • dislikes making preferences during the learning process, • is extremely realistic, and • understands the whole if she/he understands the pieces. 	<p>Sensual Learning</p> <p>A sensual learner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thinks that she/he learns best by “relating with emotions”, • prefers random processes rather than hierarchic ones, • uses emotions while solving problems, • likes being provided with various resources and choices, • dislikes the planning of her/his own learning process by others, • is too much creative, and • understands a combination of pieces if she/he understands the whole.

Fig 5: Eight Learning Styles

Adults as Learners

Part of being an effective instructor involves understanding how adults learn best. Compared to children and teens, adults have special needs and requirements as learners. Despite the apparent truth, adult learning is a relatively new area of study. The field of adult learning was pioneered by Malcom Knowles. He identified six factors that serve as sources of motivation for adult learning:

- Social relationships: to make new friends, to meet a need for associations and friendships.
- External expectations: to comply with instructions from someone else; to fulfil the expectations or recommendations of someone with formal authority.
- Social welfare: to improve ability to serve mankind, prepare for service to the community, and improve ability to participate in community work.
- Personal advancement: to achieve higher status in a job, secure professional advancement, and stay abreast of competitors.
- Escape/Stimulation: to relieve boredom, provide a break in the routine of home or work, and provide a contrast to other exacting details of life.
- Cognitive interest: to learn for the sake of learning, seek knowledge for its own sake, and to satisfy an inquiring mind. (Knowles, M. S.,1968)

Data Analysis

Team	Count	Learning Plan - Year 1 Hours	Planned as per LJ			Actual as per LJ			Avg Learning Hrs / Emp / M
			Coursera Plan	VILT Plan	Others Plan	Coursera Actual	VILT Actual	Others Actual	
Trainee BA	84	309	219	38	52	28	28	3	9.9
Trainee DE	17	346	240	30	76	37	35	6	13
Trainee DS	17	340	250	36	55	27	39	6	12
Trainee RA	27	335	239	74	23	43	39	9	15.2
Middle Manager BA	194	214	173	25	16	16	10	4	3.1
Middle Manager DE	137	139	111	16	12	18	13	6	3.6
Middle Manager DS	41	153	111	31	12	11	12	3	2.5
Middle Manager RA	133	155	113	19	22	13	14	4	3.2
Sr Manager BA	54	185	153	29	3	7	19	2	2.8
Sr Manager DE	25	195	159	27	10	3	19	7	2.9
Sr Manager DS	9	265	206	48	11	13	14	0	2.7
Sr Manager RA	31	162	109	44	9	13	14	9	3.6
Analytics Org	769	2798	2082	416	301	229	255	61	4.7

Fig-6: Cohort-wise Planned and Actual Learning Journey Hours

Mode	Hours	%
Coursera	2082	74%
VILT	416	15%
Others	301	11%
Total	2799	

Fig-6A: BAO Planned Learning Hours / Year

Mode	Hours	%
Coursera	229	42%
VILT	255	47%
Others	61	11%
Total	545	

Fig-6B: BAO Actual Learning Hours / Year

Trainee	145	15
Middle Manager	505	6
Senior Manager	119	5
Total	769	7.5

Fig-7: Weighted average of BAO Learning hours target / Employee / Month

Fig 8: % Certified Learners (who have done required learning hrs to receive Silver, Gold, Platinum certificates) in BAO

Observation(s):

- Barring one, every other cohort is behind the learning hours target.
- Average learning hours at BAO level is 4.7, way less than 7.5 (weighted average) if everyone were meeting learning hours targets.
- It's an indication that learning journeys designed for employees haven't got their buy in. It sets the stage for push-based L&D interventions wherein the outsourced L&D team is expected to nudge employees to meet their learning targets. L&D team has done **2000+** nudges for the learners in the given year.
- Self-paced learning (primarily Coursera) constitutes 74% of planned learning hours.
- Coursera Actual Hrs % of Planned stands at only **11%** at Analytics Org level. This implies that the learning journey has been packed with lots of course recommendations, way beyond the uptake capacity of learners.
- Virtual Instructor Led Trainings (VILT) actual learning hours constitutes 61% of planned VILT learning hours.
- Virtual Instructor Led Trainings (VILT) constitutes 47% of actual total learning hours. Self-paced constitutes 42%. This indicates learners' preference for VILT.

- Data suggests there isn't much difference in VILT training attendance by the certified and non-certified learners (that is learners attaining silver, gold, platinum), implying preference for VILT across all teams. This is an interesting behaviour from learners and looks quite logical, **pull for shorter duration trainings is high**. Learners can also get their learning hours easily.
- Only **37% of BAO** is certified (Silver, Gold, Platinum). This is another evidence of push based learning culture prevalent in BAO at present.

L&D Survey Data Analysis

Fig 9: L&D Survey participants vertical wise

Fig 10: L&D Survey participants cohort wise

Fig 11: 72% learners indicate they are aware of learning resources.

Fig 12: 62% learners indicate they find learning resources accessible

Fig 13: 33% learners indicate they find learning journeys highly relevant.

Fig 14: 31% learners indicate they find learning journeys always applicable to their job roles.

Fig 15: 63% learners see themselves committing 1.5-2 hrs per week.

Fig 16: 75% learners would recommend BAO learning journeys to their colleagues (NPS).

High NPS: Score of 8 or above

Low NPS: Less than 8

NPS: Net Promoter Score

Predicting NPS Using Regression

Bivariate Analysis: Between potential factors and NPS

Fig 17: Accessibility of Learning Resources and NPS

Fig 18: Learning Culture & NPS

Fig 19: Training Satisfaction & NPS

Fig 20: LJ Relevance and NPS

Fig 21: Learning Hours Commitment and NPS

Fig 22: Manager Feedback & NPS

Observation(s):

- 75% learners would recommend BAO learning journeys to their colleagues (NPS).
- Those who find learning resources accessible, have higher NPS.
- Those who perceive high learning culture have also high NPS. Senior Leadership's involvement and them leading by example makes a strong case for learning culture in the eyes of learners.
- Learners who are highly satisfied with trainings tend to have higher NPS. Most instructor led trainings are conducted virtually (VILT mode). It appears that learners value these trainings that are mostly conducted by BAO's SMEs.
- Learners who find LJ relevance tend to have higher NPS.
- Learners who commit themselves to minimum 1.5 to 2 hours of learning per week have a higher NPS. This is also a strong indicator of learners engagement.
- Manager's involvement and nudges seem to influence learners NPS.

Regression Output:

- In the regression model to predict NPS, following predictors came statistically significant:
 - Training Satisfaction (dummy coded as TS Very High etc.)
 - Manager Feedback (dummy coded as MF Regular etc.)
 - Learning Resources Accessibility (dummy coded as LR Accessible High etc.)
 - Learning Journey Relevance (dummy coded as LJ Relevance High etc.)

- Learning Hours Commitment (dummy coded as LHC High etc.)

SUMMARY OUTPUT					
Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.76				
R Square	0.57				
Adjusted R Square	0.55				
Standard Error	1.18				
Observations	330				
ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	14	584.33	41.74	30.05	8.20E-50
Residual	315	437.47	1.39		
Total	329	1021.81			

Fig 23: Regression Output – R Square, Anova Table

55% of Learners NPS score is influenced by the factors mentioned above. The predictive model would capture 95% of learners NPS within +/- 2.36.

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	3.46	0.53	6.51	3.04E-10	2.41	4.50	2.41	4.50
TS Very High	1.93	0.27	7.26	3.07E-12	1.41	2.45	1.41	2.45
TS Med High	1.31	0.23	5.58	5.23E-08	0.85	1.77	0.85	1.77
TS Very Low	0.14	0.37	0.38	7.08E-01	-0.60	0.88	-0.60	0.88
TS Med Low	-0.48	0.41	-1.19	2.36E-01	-1.29	0.32	-1.29	0.32
MF Regular	1.02	0.37	2.80	5.49E-03	0.30	1.74	0.30	1.74
MF Sometimes	0.90	0.37	2.44	1.54E-02	0.17	1.63	0.17	1.63
MF Rare	0.40	0.42	0.95	3.43E-01	-0.42	1.21	-0.42	1.21
LR Accessible High	1.20	0.29	4.13	4.67E-05	0.63	1.77	0.63	1.77
LR Accessible Med	0.82	0.29	2.80	5.47E-03	0.24	1.39	0.24	1.39
LJ Relevance High	1.18	0.45	2.62	9.13E-03	0.30	2.07	0.30	2.07
LJ Relevance Med	0.95	0.44	2.17	3.08E-02	0.09	1.82	0.09	1.82
LJ Relevance Low	0.23	0.43	0.52	6.00E-01	-0.63	1.08	-0.63	1.08
LHC High	0.79	0.31	2.57	1.08E-02	0.18	1.40	0.18	1.40
LHC Med	0.70	0.31	2.26	2.48E-02	0.09	1.31	0.09	1.31

Fig 24: Predictors and their p values

All predictors were found statistically significant.

Prediction Model for NPS:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{NPS} = & 1.93 * \text{TS Very High} + 1.31 * \text{TS Med High} + 0.14 * \text{TS Very Low} - 0.48 * \text{TS Med Low} \\ & + 1.02 * \text{MF Regular} + 0.9 * \text{MF Sometimes} + 0.4 * \text{MF Rare} + 1.2 * \text{LR Accessible High} + \\ & 0.82 * \text{LR Accessible Med} + 1.18 * \text{LJ Relevance High} + 0.95 * \text{LJ Relevance Med} + 0.23 * \\ & \text{LJ Relevance Low} + 0.79 * \text{LHC High} + 0.7 * \text{LHC Med} \end{aligned}$$

TS	Training Satisfaction
MF	Manager Feedback
LR	Learning Resources
LJ	Learning Journey
LHC	Learning Hours Commitment
NPS	Net Promoter Score

	Intercept	3.46																
Coeff	1.93	1.31	0.14	-0.48	1.02	0.90	0.40	1.20	0.82	1.18	0.95	0.23	0.79	0.70				
S No	TS Very High	TS Med High	TS Very Low	TS Med Low	MF Regular	MF Sometimes	MF Rare	LR Accessible High	LR Accessible Med	LJ Relevance High	LJ Relevance Med	LJ Relevance Low	LHC High	LHC Med	NPS	NPS Pred	Error	
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	10	8.6	1.4	
2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	10	9.6	0.4	
3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	6.0	-3.0	
4	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	10	9.0	1.0	
5	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	8	9.4	-1.4	
6	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	8	8.2	-0.2	
7	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	9	9.0	0.0	
8	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	4	5.2	-1.2	
9	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	9	7.7	1.3	
10	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	9	9.6	-0.6	
11	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	9	8.3	0.7	
12	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	10	9.6	0.4	
13	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	7	7.4	-0.4	
14	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	7	6.9	0.1	
15	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	8	8.1	-0.1	
16	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	8	9.4	-1.4	

Fig 25: Predicting NPS using prediction model

Recommendations for Pull-Based Learning and Building Learning Culture

Design Goals for Learning Journeys and Metrics

S No	Design Goals for Learning Journeys and Metrics
1	Pull based Learning Journeys
2	Aligned with BAO needs
3	Aligned with skill maps
4	Simple to understand and follow (Shouldn't overwhelm)
5	Accessible
6	Flexible (Gives roadmap but allows learners to choose best of content)
7	Consider learners feedback (L&D Survey)
8	Consider leaders feedback (One on One Meetings)
9	Data driven (aligns with learners behaviours)
10	Simple to monitor from Reward & Recognition perspective

Fig 26: Design Goals for Learning Journeys and Metrics

Simplify Learning Journeys

BAO’s existing learning journeys are exhaustive and lack focus. They may overwhelm a learner. Instead, a focussed learning journey would help the learners to align their learning efforts simultaneously giving BAO a sense of the skill gap at a granular level. This also contributes to pull based learning.

S NO	COMPETENCY	SKILL AREA	SKILL	SKILL BRIEF	COURSE LINK	ACHIEVED	EXPECTED	GAP
1	Technical / Tool	SQL	Basic SQL	Basic SQL		3	5	2
2		SQL	Advanced SQL	Adv SQL		5	7	2
3		PySpark	PySpark BDL	PySpark BDL		3	6	3
4		Big Data	Spark	Spark		2	5	3
5		SAS	SAS Enterprise Guide	Kafka		3	5	2
6		Cloud	Azure	Azure		3	5	2
7	Technical / Concepts	EDA	Data Wrangling & EDA	EDA		6	7	1
8		Story Telling	Story Telling Using Data	Story Telling		3	7	4
9		Machine Learning	Machine Learning	Machine Learning		3	6	3
10		Model Building	Model Building	Model Building		3	7	4
11	Functional	Functional	Retail Lending Analytics	Retail Lending		6	6	0
12		Functional	UPI	UPI		3	6	3
13		Functional	Database Lending Analytics	Database Lending		5	6	1
14		Functional	Credit Line Increase	Commercial Banking		2	6	4
15	Process	EDC	Informatica EDC	EDC		5	7	2
16		BAO SOP	BAO SOP (accessing tools, schema, tables etc.)	BIU SOP		5	7	2
17	Professional	Team Work	Working Effectively In Teams, Collaboration	Teamwork		3	7	4
18		Communication	Communication In Person, Virtual, Email	Communication		4	7	3

Fig 27: Illustration of Simplified Learning Journey

Fig 28: Illustration of a skill map

Senior Leadership Learning Metrics

We propose learning metrics for Senior Leadership cohort. This is based on the premise that leaders lead by example.

	# E Learning	# Book	# Leadership / Functional Talk	# Master Class
Badge Level 1	3	1	2	1
Badge Level 2	4	2	3	2
Badge Level 3	5	3	4	2

Fig 29: Senior Leadership Learning Metrics

Outcome-based learning goals for Senior Leadership:

- Self-paced learning: On Technical / Functional / Trending Topics
- Recommended Book Readings and organise book interventions. Senior Leadership discusses book insights on a given book in a panel discussion format moderated by a senior L&D person.
- Leaders learn by teaching: Leadership talks are organized and recorded on a chosen area of common interest. This has a ripple effect on the peers and a pull effect on their teams.
- Master Classes in areas identified by leadership has been recommended.

Badges will be given to leaders based on metrics defined earlier reinforcing their credibility and moral authority in inspiring their teams.

Simplify Learning Metrics

Broadly, there are following options when it comes to learning metrics:

Metric	Learning Measurement
Learning Hours	Indirect
Credit Based	Derived
Course Completions	Direct
Assessment	Direct

Fig 30: Learning Metrics

Present learning metrics is learning hours based. Not only it fails to capture the learning, it also sets the stage for learners trying to game the system. Outcome based metrics as shown below aligns naturally with learners intrinsic reinforcing pull based learning culture.

In Cohort based learning hours-based metrics, juniors need to achieve more learning hours. Not only it is confusing, but it has the unintended consequence of viewing learning as a punishment. The proposed outcome-based metric is uniform across cohorts, simple to understand and administer. However, having an integrated learning management system is needed that tags each learning as: technical, tool based, functional etc.

	Silver	Gold	Platinum	Target Hrs / Month
Trainee	70*	90	110	15
Middle Manager	40	60	80	6
Senior Manager	30	50	60	5

*: Certificates are given based on yearly learning hours

	# Technical	# Tool	# Functional	# Process	# Professional	# Total
Silver	1	2	3	1	1	8
Gold	2	3	4	1	1	11
Platinum	3	3	4	2	2	14

Fig 31: Proposed Learning Metrics

There is no one size fits all, therefore above-mentioned metrics may need to be tweaked as per organizational needs. However, the intent is to have **outcome-based metrics that are uniform across cohorts, easy to understand and remember.**

Integrate Learning Metrics into KRA

The adage, what is not measured, can't be improved holds true. Learning metrics need to be part of individual's development plan (IDP). This would drive accountability and align learners' interest towards their respective learning journeys further reinforcing pull based learning.

Designing Learning Mix

In designing learning mix, we need to reckon following:

- Learning styles vary. Some learners prefer self-paced courses. Some prefer instructor led trainings.
- Bank Analytics Organisation (BAO) is spread across locations and has employees working in hybrid mode. Given this and also considering cost, organising instructor led trainings (ILT) as a primary mode of training would be a challenge. For highly technical concepts or tools where hands on practice is desirable, ILT can be considered.
- Bank's domain specific functional trainings need to be conducted by BAO or Bank SME and recorded. Hence, for functional trainings virtual instructor led training (VILT) mode is naturally aligned.
- A large body of knowledge such as courses in Machine Learning, Deep Learning, SQL, Generative AI etc. is available as self-paced learning through MOOCs such as Coursera, edX etc.

Considering above and keeping the learning metrics into consideration, our recommendation for BAO's learning mix would be:

Learning Mode	%
ILT	20%
VILT	40%
Self Paced	40%

Levers for driving learner satisfaction and engagement

In the regression model, following predictors came statistically significant and can be used as a reference to drive learner engagement and satisfaction:

- Training Satisfaction
- Manager Feedback
- Learning Resources Accessibility
- Learning Journey Relevance
- Learning Hours Commitment

Conclusion & Future Scope of Research

The study contributes to the body of knowledge in multiple ways. It Lays out design goals for learning journeys and metrics aligned with the objective of a pull-based learning culture. It also Simplifies learning journeys making them accessible, easier to understand and implement. With this study, there is also an introduction to a role-based skill map for learners that on one hand gives clarity to learners and on another hand gives skill gap visibility to BAO setting the stage for prioritizing the training budget.

This paper emphasizes the importance of senior leadership learning metrics, empowering them with the moral authority to inspire their respective teams to accomplish learning goals. It Simplifies learning metrics for BAO to make them easier to understand and set the context for outcome-based learning. The study recommends integrating learning metrics into KRA to further reinforce pull-based learning. Further, it recommends an appropriate mix of learning mix keeping in mind organizational constraints of multiple locations, hybrid mode of work, cost etc. It Identifies levers for driving learner satisfaction and engagement.

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